

Corticospinal and corticoreticulospinal projections have discrete but complementary roles in chronic motor behaviors after stroke

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A) Electrode Placement

B) Muscle activation during BIC task

C) Muscle activation during FDI task

Supplemental Figure 2. Muscle activity recording for individuation assessment. Single dots represent individual subjects. The box plot displays the median (horizontal white line) and the interquartile range (IQR) between the first and third quartile. The whiskers show values within 1.5*IQR. **A) Electrode Placement.** Prior to arc task performance, we placed surface EMGs on the instructed muscles, biceps (BIC) and first dorsal interosseous (FDI). We also placed EMGs on muscles commonly involved in pathological synergies: middle deltoid (DEL), triceps (TRI, not visible), flexor carpi radialis (FCR), extensor digitorum (ED), and flexor digitorum superficialis (FDS). We recorded muscle co-activation during arc task performance by the BIC and FDI. Excluding the instructed muscles, those that are classically involved in flexor synergies are shown in blue text, and those involved in extensor synergies are shown in pink text. **B) Muscle activation during BIC task.** Muscle activation was higher in stroke than healthy subjects for the instructed muscle (BIC, $p = 0.017$) and all other all other sampled muscles ($p < 0.017$) except ED and FDS. In stroke subjects, muscles involved in flexor and extensor synergies were comparably active ($z = -0.4$, $p = 0.683$). In healthy subjects, there was more activity in muscles involved in extensor than flexor synergies ($z = 3.9$, $p = 0.0009$, $d = 2.3$). **C) Muscle activation during FDI task.** Muscle activation was higher in stroke than healthy subjects for the instructed muscle (FDI, $p = 0.008$) and all other sampled muscles (all $p < 0.014$). In stroke subjects, there was more activity in muscles involved in extensor than flexor synergies ($z = 2.7$, $p = 0.006$, $d = 2.1$). Similarly, in healthy subjects, there was more activity in muscles involved in extensor than flexor synergies ($z = 3.9$, $p = 0.0009$, $d = 2.4$).